

FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract. *The purpose of the article is to develop students' creative abilities and reading in the process of studying at the university. The article is based on the results of qualitative and observational studies of the authors. Qualitative research is characterized by in-depth expert conversations with specialists in the field of higher education. The authors identified factors, conditions and levels of the process of development of creativity and reading of students in higher educational institutions and analyzed its content. According to the authors, the decisive contribution to the development of student creativity is a comprehensive, systematic application of the concept of individual, procedural and environmental in accordance with three clearly defined levels of higher education. This article discusses the flourishing of creativity in higher education, various problems, as well as some factors that contribute to the development of creativity and reading in an educational environment of this type.*

Keywords: *creativity, higher education, teachers, students, pedagogical practice, creativity in higher education, professors, reading.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ТВОРЧЕСТВА И ЛЮБВИ КНИГЕ КАЧЕСТВ В ВУЗЕ

Аннотация. *Цель статьи - развитие творческих способностей студентов и чтения в процессе обучения в вузе. Статья основана на результатах качественных и наблюдательных исследований авторов. Качественное исследование характеризуется углубленными экспертными беседами со специалистами в области высшего образования. Авторы выявили факторы, условия и уровни процесса развития творчества и чтения у студентов высших учебных заведений и проанализировали его содержание. По мнению авторов, решающим вкладом в развитие студенческой креативности является комплексное, системное применение концепции индивидуального, процессуального и экологического в соответствии с тремя четко определенными уровнями высшего образования. В данной статье рассматривается расцвет творчества в высшей школе, различные проблемы, а также некоторые факторы, способствующие развитию творчества и чтения в образовательной среде данного типа.*

Ключевые слова: *творчество, высшее образование, преподаватели, студенты, педагогическая практика, творчество в высшей школе, профессора, чтение.*

INTRODUCTION.

One of the main tasks of education, which is one of the topical issues in the development of our society, is the development of thinking human capital with modern knowledge and creative thinking. One of the main factors in the growth of a person's thinking is his creative thinking, which must first of all be formed in the readership in order to develop this ability. Creativity is applicable to every field; experts determine what they find useful and innovative in the field. The higher the level of demand in each area, the higher the creativity. Creativity is inherent in every person, but people develop it under the influence of various factors or, conversely, lose it. Sensitivity to problems for the development of creativity and reading; it is

necessary to teach them to look for harmony, answers and solutions, to put forward hypotheses, to test them and to generalize the results.

For this, we can cite the fact that various events are organized in our country and the winners are awarded various prizes. Of these: “Young Reader”, “Third Renaissance”, “Startup Projects” etc.

Guilford views creativity as a multi-purpose cognitive creativity and defines it in terms of four key characteristics: fluency, flexibility, accuracy, and originality. One of the most important and leading human values is the desire for self-development, for self-expression, for the development of one's potential. Openness to innovation, the ability to make non-standard solutions, the security of the external environment, freedom of expression are the conditions for the realization of potential, self-development. A creative act consists of three systems: personality, field of activity (general practices, values, knowledge) and a community of specialists, that is a community of people who carry out their professional activities in this area.

The International Labor Organization considers creativity to be one of the basic skills and competencies required in modern life and emphasizes the need to develop creativity as part of its integration into the process of academic education and training.

The creative world in higher education is an uncertain and difficult task that requires the help of those who help and use their creative abilities. The importance of encouraging the creativity of university students is widely recognized due to the need to prepare young people for an uncertain and complex world requires the ability to use their creative abilities. Despite this recognition, it was difficult for teachers to encourage creativity in higher education. While there is a general consensus that university students are creative, educators are generally unfamiliar with creative learning environments. In addition, many factors influence creative expression in higher education, such as student resistance, the organizational structure of universities, the quality of teachers, and teaching practices. Creativity is now increasingly recognized by scholars and experts in various fields (e.g Davis, 2004; Robinson, 2013). Research on the development of creativity shows that in today's society, those who do not use their creative abilities fail in one or more aspects of life, which is a necessity for our survival. Creativity helps people make better use of opportunities and respond more seriously to the challenges of their personal and professional lives, as well as those challenges. Creative behavior also enhances the quality of life, the expression of which is usually accompanied by a sense of satisfaction and pleasure, which is one of the key elements of emotional well-being and mental health. Creativity is also important in the business world and, as a result, is an important factor in the innovation and success of organizations.

Led to further improvement in the quality of education and innovation with the aim of negotiating with a number of countries and implementing educational policies aimed at developing the creative abilities of students. Providing opportunities for teaching creativity has become an important part of higher education. In higher education, it is necessary to recognize the important role of creativity in preparing students for a fuzzy and complex world of activity, which requires professors to use their creative abilities. An important role of creativity in society is knowledge orientation. For these reasons, university professors need to be able to create an environment that includes strategies, approaches, methods and recommendations aimed at developing the creative abilities of students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the importance of changes in our national education system to ensure the effective development of creative abilities in higher education students. The development of creative abilities in the educational process can be viewed from different points of view. One of the approaches to the study of creativity in education is associated with the introduction of a competency-based approach, which is based on the consideration of creativity, taking into account the interdependence of several components: methodological, procedural, personal and panoramic. According to this approach, creative competence is the ability to work effectively and inventively in conditions of uncertainty to solve specific practical problems, knowledge and experience, the willingness to flexibly use the acquired knowledge, to self-education and self-realization, improvement. Depending on the topic, creativity in education is studied in four aspects: individual (creativity of employees and students), group (communication, cooperation), procedural, institutional (factors and environmental conditions).

It is necessary to develop as much as possible measures to form and develop the creative potential of students in the preparation of creative specialists of higher educational institutions, as well as in the implementation of methods of work in certain specialties and areas of education. A special problem in this regard is the imbalance between the development and understanding of creativity by all participants in the educational and labor processes. Ways to solve the problem through the development of activity, focus on results and preparation for additional education and skills, learning activities and a favorable climate, curriculum will also be considered.

The development of creativity in higher education is useful both for people and their personal achievements, and for society. Because all employers have mastered effective strategies, problem solving, critical and independent thinking to deal with situations that can arise, rapid changes and unpredictable problems.

The development of the creative abilities of students depends on the extent to which the creativity of teachers is developed, so it can develop the creative abilities of students. In addition, the type of leadership and leadership of the teacher and his or her ability to understand students are also related to creativity. There are differences between how students and teachers perceive and understand creativity. While students emphasize creativity primarily as an individual or process feature, professors understand student creativity through personal reflection, independent decision making, curiosity and motivation, and creating and developing new things.

Another factor contributing to the development of creativity in higher education is the need to promote an institutional culture that emphasizes creativity and its expression rather than traditional forms of scientific development. the need for cultural change in higher education, including as one of its elements “helping teachers understand and enhance their creativity and recognize this as an integral part of their professional skills”, as well as teachers and the need to provide a model environment that encourages thinking and personal student development. Since the role of teachers in developing the creative potential of students is important, creativity should be a widely covered topic in the professional development of teachers, in preparing teachers to recognize and develop the creative abilities of students. Teachers should also be aware of the pedagogical practices that can be applied in the classroom to develop student creativity and the various factors that influence creative expression. To help the university create conditions for its faculty. Among other strategies for the development of creativity in higher education, the following strategies can be used:

- Have enough time and audience in the curriculum to allow students to develop their creativity;
- Giving students the freedom to work in new and exciting ways in a variety of work environments that are diverse enough to allow all students to be creative;
- Engage students in real, challenging, and fun work;
- Developing an assessment that achieves unpredictable results;
- Creating an office environment that encourages thinking and personal development of staff and students;
- Continuation of academic discussions and conversations with various stakeholders about the nature of the topic and the role of creativity in it. Here are some tips on how to view or make an appointment for hair extensions:
 - Consider prior knowledge of student;
 - Take time for dialogue, listen respectfully to students;
 - Help students overcome emotional blocks such as fear of making mistakes and fear of criticism;
 - Incentives should cover topics that interest students the most;
 - Vary the teaching strategies used in the lesson;
 - Criticize students only constructively;
 - Encourage students to come up with new ideas;
 - Ask provocative questions;
 - Maintain a positive relationship with students;
 - Raise. A psychologically safe environment in which students are not afraid to express themselves;
 - Understand individual differences in behavior and problem-solving skills;

The development of the creative abilities of future teachers is of great importance in the process of their education, especially during the years of professional training of teachers of higher education. This should include not only a separate subject of creativity in the teacher training program, but also through a real creative developmental pedagogical and learning environment in which future teachers experience what they can do as students and then can demonstrate their creativity and be able to find their own way.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the factors discussed in the literature that explains the use of strategies for the development of creativity in universities is the preschool experience of teachers. Beghetto (2010) argues that the influence of teaching on beliefs, knowledge, and teaching practice is related to the previous student's deep experience.

According to John Baer, knowledge, skills, abilities, attitudes, new ideas and ideas do not develop in a vacuum, they always differ in direction and specialization, so the development of creativity is a matter of priority.

Research on the Russian and international labor market shows that that the specificity of the demand for and need for specialists lies in creativity, the ability to have one's own opinion in a team and work independently, independently solve problem situations, find new ways of existence and relevance of human qualities.

The influence of additional courses and sociocultural structures is also important in educating students' creative culture that student creativity is a key issue in every field of

pedagogical science, the importance of teacher creativity is rarely overlooked, if it does not take into account future perspectives, proximity can be beneficial for group activity creativity. The opportunities for the development of creativity in higher education are educational activities and an environment of free creativity, the curriculum, the warm attitude of teachers and students, as well as the ability to understand each other, plays one of the most important roles in the learning process; therefore, this issue should not be ignored in the process of professional development of students of higher educational institutions. Seminars have a positive impact on the production of ideas, creativity of decisions and the effectiveness of leadership. The introduction of teaching methods into the educational process reveals the creative potential of higher education students.

CONCLUSION

Teachers and students of universities face many problems. One of the issues discussed in this article is the need to promote a culture of creativity among teachers and students that promotes creativity and reading. In today's information age, professionals are needed who can create new ideas, meet high demand, create innovative models, and propose competitive projects and implement them. The success of such activities lies in the high popularity of reading among students, the formation and development of high creative abilities among such specialists. It is no coincidence that the state and private business want to hire young professionals, distinguished creative thinkers and innovators from among their graduates. The huge creative potential of young people, competently developed and methodically worked out and implemented, will bring great benefits to employers. It is necessary to develop adequate mechanisms for the formation and development of creative potential in students in the performance of their labor functions. Creating an innovative environment that provides active learning and encourages students to use their creative abilities in conjunction with a variety of skills should be considered a topical issue for university teachers. In addition, professional development programs for higher education teachers should be developed. We hope that this article will contribute to highlighting the importance of creativity in higher education. While some professors recognize the importance of creativity, they need to do more research and work to create a higher education culture that supports and encourages creativity.

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